

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

**2026-YIL / IYUN/6-SON,
V-QISM**

Google Scholar

ISSN

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, iyun.
V-qism*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVDA ESG TAMOYILLARINI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI.....	12
I. R. Berdikulova	
TEKSTIL SANOATIDA SUV ISTE'MOLI VA QAYTA ISHLASH ULUSHI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK: 20 DAVLAT MISOLIDA KORRELYATSIYA VA K-MEANS KLASTER TAHLILI.....	16
Zayniyev Diyorbek Zokir o'g'li	
Turobova Hulkar Rustamovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BIZNES BIRLASHUVLARINI HISOBGA OLISHNI MHXS (IFRS) 3 ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	24
Davletov Ikrom Raximberganovich	
VINOCHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALAR AUDITINI TASHKIL QILISH VA O'TKAZISH TARTIBI.....	33
Jo'rayev Dilshod Xudoyqulovich	
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЮ ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИМИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯМИ	38
Абдуллаева М.Б.	
AGROSANOAT MAJMUASIDA INTEGRATSION TUZILMALARNING ISTIQBOLLI SHAKLLARINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	44
Murodov Sherzodbek Murod o'g'li	
RESPUBLIKADA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING BOZOR MEXANIZMI.....	51
Kalandarova Elnura Muzaffar qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN MAHALLALARDA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISHGA KO'MAKLASHISH.....	55
Niyozov Zuxur Davronovich	
Yarlaqabov Faxriddin Baxodir o'g'li	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ОТЧЕТА О ФИНАНСОВОМ ПОЛОЖЕНИИ КОМПАНИИ В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С ТРЕБОВАНИЯМИ МСФО	58
Худойкулова Дилора Дилмуродовна	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING INVESTITSİYALARI TARKIBI VA ULARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINING IQTISODIY TAHLILI.....	64
Karimova Saodatxon Ulug'bek qizi	
XALQARO MOLİYAVIY HISOBOT STANDARTLARIGA MUVOFIQ JORIY AKTIVLARNI HISOBGA OLISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	71
Mavlyanova Dilobar Maxkamovna	
DAVLAT TOMONIDAN TURIZM SOHASINI MOLİYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	77
Karimova Dilafruz Sadriddin qizi	
МЕТОДЫ АНАЛИЗА ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ В РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	82
Ахмедова(Жабборова) Нилуфар Икболжон кизи	
AHOLI ZICH JOYLASHGAN HUDUDLARDA KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IJTIMOIY-IQTISODIY OMILLARI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA TAHLILI	89
Bo'stonova Nilufar Abdusmatovna	
Nematjonova Risolatxon Dilshodbek qizi	
JANUBIY KOREYA TAJRIBASIDA CHIQINDILARNI BOSHQARISHDA EPR TIZIMI VA RAQAMLI YECHIMLARINING O'RNI	94
Otarbayev Zamir Zairovich	

SANOAT SALOHİYATI SAMARADORLIGINI INVESTISIYALAR ASOSIDA OSHIRISHNING MINTAQAVIY XUSUSIYATLARI	100
Urazaliyev Bekzod Sultanbayevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ НАВЫКИ КАК ФАКТОР КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ЖЕНСКИХ КАДРОВ НА ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	107
Дониёрова Зухрабону Алишер кизи	
TURIZM SUG'URTASI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	113
Хо'jamov Akbar Bahriddinovich	
KELAJAKDAGI GLOBAL VA MINTAQAVIY IQLIM O'ZGARISHI HAMDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH ZARURIYATI.....	118
Djumayev Askar Xaydarovich	
SAMARQAND VILOYATI UMUMIY OVQATLANISH KORXONALARIDA RESURSLARNI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGI.....	123
Erdonov Muhammadamin Erdon o'g'li	
Qahhorova Nargiza Qahramonovna	
Rafiqjonov Damir Raxim o'g'li	
Jamilov Firdavs Otabek o'g'li	
ПУТИ РАСШИРЕНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ БАНКОВСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬЮ	129
Норкулов Хабибулло	
Абдурасулова Шахзода	
Бахриддинов Дилшодбек	
NATIV BRENDING VOSITASI SIFATIDA UGC VA EGC: GLOBAL TENDENSIYALAR VA O'ZBEKISTON BOZORIGA MOSLASHUV	135
Yuldasheva Mahliyo Baxtiyor qizi	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILARGA XIZMAT KO'RSATISHDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH ORQALI SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINING SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI	138
Shamsiyev O'ktam Sayfitdinovich	
НАУЧНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И ПРИНЦИПЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВОГО МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ ПРИ УПРАВЛЕНИИ БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССАМИ	147
Джуманов А.А.	
BANK SEKTORIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA XARAJAT SAMARADORLIGI: XALQARO TAJRIBA ASOSIDA EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	157
Masharipova Durdona Ulug'bekovna	
РАЗВИТИЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ ПРИНЯТИЯ РЕШЕНИЙ.....	164
Джуманов А.А.	
DAVLAT XARIDLARIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTGA ASOSLANGAN NARXLAR MODULINI JORIY ETISH: KORRUPSIYAGA QARSHI KOMPLAYENS, HISOBDORLIK VA RAQOBATNI KUCHAYTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	174
Rahmanov Furqat Temirovich	
АНАЛИЗ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АЛЬТМАНА ПРИ ОЦЕНКЕ ФИНАНСОВОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	179
Ибрагимов Гайратжон Артикович	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISHNINZ ZAMONAVIY MODELLARI VA KOMPLAYENSNAZORAT TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	186
Fayziyev Sherzod Djunaydilloyevich	
SUN'IY INTELLEKTNING MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGI VA MOBILIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	192
Shakarov Zafar Gafforovich	

URGUT ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONASIDA SANOAT TARMOQLARINI KLASTERLASH SAMARADORLIGINING TAHLILI	198
Boboqulov Sanjar Baxronkulovich	
Qurbonov Tolmasjon Namoz o'g'li	
Uzoqov Rafiq O'lmas o'g'li	
INFRATUZILMA INVESTITSİYALARINING AHOLI FAROVONLIGIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI	204
Jiyanov Laziz Najimovich	
«ЗЕЛЁНОЕ» ВОДОСНАБЖЕНИЕ В ЗАСУШЛИВЫХ РЕГИОНАХ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ДЛЯ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ	210
Курбанова Дилфуза Махсудовна	
TALABALARNING KASBIY KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIKPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	217
Karimova Feruza Xamidullayevna	
PAXTACHILIKDA ZAMONAVIY AGROTEKNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH VA EKOLOGIK MUVOZANAT TA'MINLASHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI.....	221
Ishniyazov Zoxid Normamatovich	
FUQAROLAR MUROJAATLARI MA'LUMOTLARI ASOSIDA HUDUDLARNING IJTIMOIIYIQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH DARAJASINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	226
Inomov Daniyar Valijonovich	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BILAN OPERATSIYALARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: HOLAT TAHLILI VA TAVSIYALAR.....	232
Niyozov Zuhur Davronovich	
Xolmurotov Sardor	
Haydaraliyev Avaz	
YAQIN SHARQDA TURIZM EKSPORTI STRATEGIYALARI VA ULARNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI: BAA VA SAUDIYA ARABISTONI TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA QIYOSIY TAHLIL	238
Tolibova Aziza To'lqin qizi	
BANKLARDA IJARA MUOMALALARINI TARTIBGA SOLUVCHI ME'YORIY - HUQUQIY ASOSLAR VA XALQARO STANDARTLAR.....	243
Sativaldiyeva Gulchexra Xudayberdiyevna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI KORXONALARIDA STRATEGIK RISK-MENEJMENT TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	247
Masharipova Sevara	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	251
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
Muhammadjonova Iroda Bahodir qizi	
BALIQCILIK TARMOG'INI INTENSIV RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	256
Iskandar Yunusov	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BARQAROR QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI: AGROEKOLOGIK VA IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY YONDASHUVLAR INTEGRATSIYASI	262
Mirzanov Berdak Joldasbeviç	
RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALARNING IPOTEKA KREDITLASH JARAYONINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARIGA TA'SIRI	268
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihol	
CHORVACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI: METODOLOGIYA VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	273
Aysachev Abdulfotix Abdulfaizovich	

O'ZBEKISTONDA XIZMATLAR EKSPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI.....	278
Ruziyeva Nigina Baxtiyorovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM TIZIMIDA OLIB BORILGAN ISLOHOTLAR (MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TIZIMI MISOLIDA)	284
G.A. Norbo'tayeva	
YASHIL MARKETING VA ESG INTEGRATSIYASI: STATISTIK TAHLIL VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	288
Charos G'ayratova	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ СИСТЕМ И ОБЗОР ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ ПРИНЯТИЯ РЕШЕНИЙ.....	294
Джуманов, А.А.	
RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLARDA INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH — IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTNING MUHIM OMILI.....	303
Bayitova Rohatoy Bahrom qizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRUVCHILARNI SUG'URTA MEKANIZMLARI ORQALI MOLIYALASH MASALALARI	307
Xakimov Zafar Ibragimovich	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGI ORQALI TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINING BARQAROR FAOLIYAT YURITISHINI TA'MINLASH MUAMMOLARI.....	314
Ahrorqulov Jonibek Otabek o'g'li	
FOOD PRICE VOLATILITY AND ITS EFFECTS ON LOW-INCOME HOUSEHOLDS	320
Rakhmatova Mukhlisa Dilshod qizi	
SUN'IY INTELLEKTNING O'ZBEKISTON SOLIQ TIZIMI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	327
Hamidova Shahzoda Odiljanovna	
MHS VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR KREDITLARI: MAMLAKATLARARO EMPIRIK TAHLIL.....	331
Davronbek Matyakubovich Matkarimov	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OLIY TA'LIM XIZMATLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ZARURATI.....	336
Xasanova Yulduz Kayumovna	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA ALOQA KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	340
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPING BROKERAGE AND UNDERWRITING ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	345
Niyozov Zukhur	
Barnoyev Mirfayoz	
Yadgarov Avaz	

PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPING BROKERAGE AND UNDERWRITING ACTIVITIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN

Niyozov Zukhur

PhD in Economics, Acting Professor of the Department of Banking
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Barnoyev Mirfayoz

4th-year student in Banking and Auditing
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Yadgarov Avaz

4th-year student in Banking and Auditing
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract. This article examines the current state and development prospects of brokerage and underwriting activities of commercial banks in Uzbekistan within the context of ongoing capital market reforms. Drawing on data from the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, the World Bank, Moody's Rating Agency, and the Tashkent Stock Exchange, the study identifies structural constraints, quantifies growth dynamics, and proposes policy recommendations to deepen bank-driven investment banking services. Findings indicate that while the banking sector has expanded nearly ninefold in nominal asset terms since 2017, its participation in capital market intermediation remains nascent. The paper argues that the commercialization of brokerage and underwriting functions within banks represents a critical mechanism for bridging the financing gap between capital-seeking enterprises and institutional investors.

Keywords: commercial banks, brokerage, underwriting, capital market, Uzbekistan, investment banking, securities

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda kapital bozorini isloh qilish jarayonlari sharoitida tijorat banklarining brokerlik va anderrayting faoliyatining hozirgi holati hamda rivojlanish istiqbollari o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki, Jahon banki, Moody's reyting agentligi va Toshkent Respublika fond birjasi ma'lumotlari asosida tarkibiy cheklovlar aniqlangan, o'sish dinamikasi baholangan hamda banklar tomonidan ko'rsatiladigan investitsion bank xizmatlarini chuqurlashtirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, 2017-yildan buyon bank sektori aktivlari nominal jihatdan qariyb to'qqiz barobar oshgan bo'lsa-da, banklarning kapital bozorida vositachilik faoliyatidagi ishtiroki hali boshlang'ich bosqichda qolmoqda. Maqolada banklarda brokerlik va anderrayting funksiyalarini tijoratlashtirish kapitalga ehtiyoj sezayotgan korxonalar hamda institutsional investorlar o'rtasidagi moliyalashtirish tafovutini kamaytirishning muhim mexanizmi sifatida asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tijorat banklari, brokerlik faoliyati, anderrayting, kapital bozori, O'zbekiston, investitsion bank ishi, qimmatli qog'ozlar.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются современное состояние и перспективы развития брокерской и андеррайтинговой деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана в контексте проводимых реформ рынка капитала. На основе данных Центрального банка Узбекистана, Всемирного банка, рейтингового агентства Moody's и Ташкентской фондовой биржи в исследовании выявляются структурные ограничения, оценивается динамика роста и предлагаются практические рекомендации по углублению инвестиционно-банковских услуг, осуществляемых банками. Результаты исследования показывают, что, несмотря на почти девятикратный рост банковского сектора в номинальном выражении с 2017 года, его участие в посреднических операциях на рынке капитала пока находится на начальном этапе. В статье обосновывается, что коммерциализация брокерских и андеррайтинговых функций банков является важным механизмом преодоления разрыва между предприятиями, нуждающимися в капитале, и институциональными инвесторами.

Ключевые слова: коммерческие банки, брокерская деятельность, андеррайтинг, рынок капитала, Узбекистан, инвестиционный банкинг, ценные бумаги.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan has undertaken comprehensive economic and financial sector reforms since 2017, transforming its previously predominantly state-led financial architecture toward a market-oriented system. The banking sector has historically functioned as the dominant intermediary, accounting for approximately 95 percent of total financial sector assets as of end-2024 (World Bank, 2025). Yet the capital market — encompassing equity, debt, and derivative instruments — has remained underdeveloped relative to peer economies at comparable income levels.

International experience demonstrates that commercial banks capable of performing dual roles — as traditional deposit-lending intermediaries and as capital market participants through brokerage and underwriting — contribute significantly to financial deepening. In Germany, South Korea, and Japan, universal banking models have historically channeled long-term corporate financing through bank-led securities activities. For Uzbekistan, where state-owned commercial banks (SOCBs) hold 65 percent of total banking assets (Moody's, 2025), the transition toward investment banking services represents both an opportunity and an important institutional priority.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Banking Sector Overview As of end-2024, Uzbekistan's banking sector comprised 36 banks: nine state-owned commercial banks (SOCBs), eight private foreign banks, and 19 private domestic banks (World Bank, 2025). Total banking sector assets reached \$59.5 billion, equivalent to 53 percent of GDP — a nearly ninefold increase in nominal terms since 2017 (Moody's, 2025; IMF, 2025). Key sectoral indicators are presented in Table 1.

Capital Market Development Uzbekistan's equity capital market is anchored by the Republican Stock Exchange "Tashkent" (RSE), established in 1994. As of January 2026, the exchange listed 85 ordinary and 38 preferred shares with a combined market capitalization of approximately \$9.7 billion (Asia Frontier Capital, 2026). Projections from Statista indicate that total stock market capitalization could reach \$20.06 billion in 2025, reflecting rapid post-reform growth.

Table 1.
Capital Market Development Indicators¹

Indicator	Value / Period
RSE market capitalization	\$9.7 billion (Jan 2026)
Projected market capitalization	\$20.06 billion (2025, Statista)
Number of listed companies (ordinary shares)	85
OTC-listed companies	~677
Exchange transactions in 2023	411,900
Value of exchange transactions in 2023	UZS 2.7 trillion (~\$215 million)
Increase in transactions vs 2022	5-fold
Trading volume surge (Oct 2023 vs Oct 2022)	8.5-fold
Open brokerage accounts	~50,000 (vs 36 million population)

A landmark development occurred in May 2026, when Uzbekistan's National Investment Fund (UzNIF), managed by Franklin Templeton, completed a dual listing on the London Stock Exchange and the Tashkent Stock Exchange — the country's first-ever international equity offering — generating over \$603.6 million and attracting \$2.8 billion in investor demand, with cornerstone investors including BlackRock and Franklin Resources (Dunyo Information Agency, 2026).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applies descriptive, comparative, and institutional analysis methods. The research is based on secondary data from the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, the World Bank, the IMF, Moody's, the Tashkent Stock Exchange, and official legal documents regulating capital market development.

Commercial bank participation in brokerage services in Uzbekistan has historically been constrained by regulatory design: until recently, banks operated primarily as custodians of securities rather than active market

¹ Sources: Asia Frontier Capital (2026), Tashkent Stock Exchange, DFO Singapore (2025), Stockscope.uz

makers. However, the expansion of the Tashkent Stock Exchange and the three landmark IPOs conducted in 2023 catalyzed bank engagement in brokerage. Notably, the Uztelecom IPO (2023) — which issued 5,542,046 new common shares representing 2 percent of authorized capital at a price range of UZS 6,000–10,000 per share — was facilitated by a consortium comprising Portfolio Investments, the National Bank of Uzbekistan (NBU), and Sanoat Qurilish Bank (SQB) (Stockscope.uz, 2023). This transaction demonstrated the capacity of state-affiliated commercial banks to serve underwriting and distribution functions. Brokerage commission structures remain thin: the Uztelecom IPO set total commissions at 1 percent, of which 0.77 percent went to the broker, 0.20 percent to the exchange, and 0.03 percent to the Central Securities Depository. The narrow commission environment reflects limited market competition and an early-stage fee-based service environment.

Table 2.
Selected Underwriting Transactions in Uzbekistan (2023–2026)²

Transaction	Year	Structure	Key Banks Involved	Approx. Size
UzAuto Motors IPO	2023	Domestic equity offering	State-linked banks	Not disclosed
Uztelecom IPO	2023	2% stake, 5.54 million shares	NBU, SQB, Portfolio Investments	~UZS 50 billion
Uzbekinvest IPO (preferred)	2023	Preferred shares	N/A	Not disclosed
UzNIF dual listing (LSE + RSE)	2026	International equity offering	Franklin Templeton (lead)	\$603.6 million

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Demand-Side Constraints

Retail investor participation remains relatively low: approximately 50,000 brokerage accounts exist in Uzbekistan, representing 0.14 percent of a population of 36 million (Stockscope.uz). By comparison, Russia's Moscow Exchange had 31.8 million open accounts as of March 2023, representing approximately 22 percent of the population. Low financial literacy, limited awareness of equity investment, and competition from high-yield bank deposits — which offered up to 27 percent annually in 2023 — limit demand for brokerage services.

Regulatory and Policy Framework

The Government of Uzbekistan has signaled strong commitment to capital market development through a layered reform architecture:

- Capital Market Roadmap 2023–2025: approved to accelerate securities market development with explicit milestones for IPOs, bond issuance, and infrastructure modernization [1];
- National Agency of Perspective Projects (NAPP): appointed as an independent capital market regulator in September 2023, replacing the previously dispersed regulatory framework;
- Retail Investment Incentive (June 2024): individuals investing in listed bonds or equities receive a 12 percent income tax exemption, subject to a 12-month lock-up [1];
- NAPP Order No. 3610 (February 2025): approved the Regulation on underwriting activities in the securities market, enabling the formal development of underwriting mechanisms in Uzbekistan [2].
- Law on Privatization (ZRU-907, February 2024): consolidated privatization rules, enabling state asset sales through exchange trading — creating a pipeline for underwriting mandates [3];
- Tashkent International Financial Centre (TIFC): established as a special financial centre aimed at positioning Tashkent as a regional financial hub and expanding the institutional framework for investment and capital market services [4].

Development Scenarios and Policy Recommendations

Under the current trajectory, brokerage account penetration may reach 200,000–300,000, or 0.5–0.8 percent of the population, by 2028, supported by the retail investment incentive scheme and expanding OTC market access. IPO activity is projected to yield 3–5 new listings annually, primarily state-owned enterprise privatizations, with commercial banks serving as consortium members rather than sole underwriters. If the proposed Tashkent International Financial Centre becomes operational and foreign investor access to the local exchange expands — as projected by the Tashkent Stock Exchange's management — market capitalization could approach \$30–40 billion by 2028. Under this scenario, leading commercial banks, including NBU, SQB,

² Sources: *bne IntelliNews* (2024), *Stockscope.uz*, *IndexBox* (2026)

and Xalqbank, could develop dedicated investment banking divisions capable of originating, structuring, and distributing securities independently.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Uzbekistan's commercial banks are entering an important stage of development. The banking sector's strong capitalization — with a CAR persistently above 17 percent — combined with a government-driven privatization pipeline and an emerging regulatory framework for underwriting creates favorable conditions for the expansion of bank-led brokerage and underwriting services. The fivefold increase in exchange transactions in 2023, the country's first-ever international IPO in 2026, and the introduction of retail investor incentives signal that market demand is gradually increasing. Nevertheless, structural barriers — including limited retail investor penetration at 0.14 percent, incomplete settlement infrastructure, high deposit interest competition, and concentrated banking ownership — may slow organic development unless supported by targeted policy measures. The international experience of Korea, Kazakhstan, and the Baltic states demonstrates that the development of investment banking within commercial banks requires not merely deregulation but also proactive capacity-building frameworks.

REFERENCES

1. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2023, September 2). Resolution No. RP-291 “On additional measures for the development of the capital market”. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6590029>
2. National Agency for Perspective Projects of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2025, February 19). Order No. 15 “On approval of the Regulation on underwriting activities in the securities market”. Registered by the Ministry of Justice on February 28, 2025, Registration No. 3610. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/docs/7410493>
3. Republic of Uzbekistan. (2024, February 14). Law No. ZRU-907 “On Privatization of State Property”. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6800650>
4. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2026, March 30). Decree No. DP-48 “On the establishment of the Tashkent International Financial Center”. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/docs/8107014>
5. World Bank. (2025). Uzbekistan: Financial Sector Assessment. Washington, DC: World Bank.
6. International Monetary Fund. (2025). Republic of Uzbekistan: Financial Sector Assessment Program — Financial System Stability Assessment. IMF Country Report No. 25/145. Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund.
7. UzDaily. (2025, March 1). Moody's: Uzbekistan's banking system is resilient but still dependent on market financing. UzDaily.
8. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2024, December 24). Information on major indicators of commercial banks as of December 1, 2024. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
9. Asia Frontier Capital. (2026). About Uzbekistan: Capital market statistics. AFC Uzbekistan Fund.
10. Republican Stock Exchange “Toshkent”. (2023, December 22). The first day of trading in shares of Uztelecom and Uzbekinvest on the Republican Stock Exchange “Toshkent”. Republican Stock Exchange “Toshkent”.
11. bne IntelliNews. (2024, February 10). Tashkent Stock Exchange raising its game on marked gains in reform and retail. bne IntelliNews.
12. bne IntelliNews. (2025, June 22). Uzbek capital market reforms unlock corporate funding boom and fuel investor demand. bne IntelliNews.
13. Kosta Legal. (2025, February 7). Uzbekistan legal newsletter: February 2025. Kosta Legal.
14. Dunyo Information Agency. (2026, May 20). National Investment Fund of Uzbekistan has listed its shares on the London and Tashkent stock exchanges. Dunyo Information Agency.
15. Stockscope.uz. (2023, December 29). The Uztelecom IPO: Understanding Uzbekistan's stock market landscape. Stockscope.uz.
16. Statista. (2025). Stocks — Uzbekistan: Market capitalization projection. Statista Market Insights.
17. Preiss, R. M. (2025, June 24). The evolution and outlook of Uzbekistan's equity market. DFO Singapore.
18. U.S. Department of State. (2025). 2025 Investment Climate Statements: Uzbekistan. U.S. Department of State.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz HAKIMOV

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Hasan MAQSUDOV

2026. № 6/5

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>